

1 An in vitro hepatitis C infection model.

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7 While cancers of the breast, lung and prostate predominate in the developed world, hepatocellular
8 carcinoma (HCC), cancer of the liver, is a leading cause of death in the developing world. HCC is caused
9 by exposure to mutagens like aflatoxin in the diet or alcohol from consumption, or following viral infection
10 with Hepatitis B or Hepatitis C virus. HCV is considered to possess greater transformation potential than
11 HBV. We studied HCV infection at the whole transcriptome level, across multiple infection models, to
12 understand viral infection resulting in cancer at the systems level. HCV infection resulted in early
13 activation of PARP9 and PARP14, XRN1 and the OAS signaling pathway. Lambda interferons Ifn13 and
14 Ifn14 were induced rapidly following HCV infection in primary human hepatocytes, as was CCL28.
15 *Hepadnaviridae* RNA virus was capable of activating Apobec3 family editors Apobec3f and Apobec3g.
16 Zbp1, ADAR, DHX58 and RIG-1 were the major nucleic acid sensors activated as a result of Hepatitis C
17 infection. We used transcriptomics and cell culture models of infection to describe the basic transcriptional
18 elements of infection with a liver-tropic virus with high transformation potential.

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21 Citations

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24 inflammatory mRNAs by spatiotemporally distinct mechanisms. *Cell*, 161(5), pp.1058-1073.